

E3.3.2: Initial Design for Distributed AI Operations in 6G v1.0

Fecha de Publicación: 30/09/2023

**[6GENABLERS-AI]
[6GENABLERS]**

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	PT2
Líder del PT	i2CAT
Editor Principal	Hatim Chergui
Contribuyentes	Irian Leyva, Shuaib Siddiqui
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v0.7	Hatim Chergui		20/09/2023	
v0.8	Irian Leyva		26/09/2023	
v1.0	Hatim Chergui, Irian Leyva		27/09/2023	

1 Table of Contents

1	Table of Contents	3
2	List of Tables	4
3	List of Figures	5
4	List of Acronyms	6
5	Executive Summary	7
6	Introduction	8
7	MLOps for Network Automation: State-of-the-Art Review	9
7.1	Research and Standardization Relevant to MLOps	9
7.1.1	Research	9
7.1.2	Standardization	10
7.2	Gaps Analysis of MLOps for Networks	10
8	Distributed MLOps Architecture for Future-Proof 6G Networks	12
8.1	SliceOps: Transparent MLOps Architecture for 6G	12
8.1.1	SliceOps Lifecycle	12
8.1.2	ETSI ZSM Compliance	14
8.1.3	O-RAN Slicing Compliance	14
8.2	Benefits of the Architecture	15
9	Tools to Implement the Architecture	17
9.1	MLOps Tools	17
9.2	E2E MLOps Platforms	18
10	Conclusion	20

2 List of Tables

Table 1 MLOps platforms supported capabilities in the MLOps phases..... 19

3 List of Figures

Figure 1 AI/ML plane. 12

Figure 2 The SliceOps workflow including monitoring, re-training, and deploying ML model as a service. 13

Figure 3 Kubeflow model architecture..... 18

4 List of Acronyms

AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
DevOps	Development and Operations
DoF	Degree of Freedom
E2AP	E2 Application Protocol
E2SM	E2 Service Model
HD	High Definition
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life-cycle Management
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLaaS	ML as a Service
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RIC	Radio Intelligent Controller
RL	Reinforcement Learning
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SoA	State-of-the-Art
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
XAI	eXplainable AI

5 Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the works carried out in task A3.1 of the project 6GENABLERS, IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10, which investigates the AI/ML Operations (MLOps) for the adoption of distributed intelligence at various levels (including federated and distributed learning), ranging from edge devices to cloud sites, and including training and inference operations, lifecycle management (LCM) and operation of AI processes. After a brief introduction, the report reviews the literature of MLOps for network automation, where both research and standardization aspects are considered, followed with a gap analysis that unveils that for a practical deployment of MLOps in future-proof 6G networks, the stakeholders in network slicing ecosystem seek natively embedding MLOps into the network architecture while enhancing the interpretability of the black-box AI decision-making process to attain human trust. The document then delves into the proposed architecture, dubbed *SliceOps* which consists of gathering the AI models LCM in a dedicated AI plane in the form of a standalone cross-domain slice. The compliance with ETSI ZSM and O-RAN is also discussed in this respect, and the benefits of the architecture highlighted. Finally, an important section covers the tools/platforms that can be adopted to implement the architecture.

6 Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving world of telecommunications, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) into network operations has become imperative. The promise of 6G networks, with their unprecedented speed and capabilities, presents a unique opportunity to revolutionize the way we manage and optimize networks. However, realizing this potential requires addressing several critical challenges in Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) within the context of network slicing. The stakeholders in the network slicing ecosystem are seeking innovative solutions that seamlessly integrate MLOps into the network architecture while simultaneously enhancing the interpretability of AI decision-making processes. Achieving human trust in AI-driven networks is paramount. Much like the separation between the user plane (UP) and control plane (CP), a modular and scalable integration of AI/ML as a native component into the future-proof 6G architecture necessitates consolidating all MLOps into a dedicated plane. This plane can be designed as a distributed cross-domain slice, managing the lifecycle of AI models, and delivering them as artifacts tailored to the target technological domain of a network slice. This approach promotes model reusability, reduces training workloads, and, consequently, reduces the carbon footprint. This innovative 6GENABLERS-AI architecture is aptly termed "SliceOps." To implement this architecture, a variety of open-source platforms, such as Kubeflow, MLflow, and Polyaxon, are available. These platforms simplify the management of all stages of the ML lifecycle, making it more straightforward, reliable, and efficient.

In the pages that follow, we delve deeper into the concept of SliceOps, exploring its benefits, implementation strategies, and its pivotal role in ushering in the era of AI-driven 6G networks. It represents a paradigm shift in the way we approach network management, ensuring that AI and ML are seamlessly woven into the fabric of future-proof telecommunications.

7 MLOps for Network Automation: State-of-the-Art Review

This section reviews the recent endeavours to integrate MLOps into wireless networks, as an enabler of AI-driven automation. It starts with research efforts and then delves into standardization aspects. Finally, a gap analysis is presented.

7.1 Research and Standardization Relevant to MLOps

7.1.1 Research

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in intelligent resource orchestration and the need for MLOps and eXplainable AI (XAI) in various domains. Indeed, Samaras et al. introduced an MLOps automation platform for optimized network slice Life-cycle Management (LCM) using a cloud-native approach¹. Their event-based framework enables zero-touch MLOps, automatically adapting and optimizing the system based on the accuracy performance of the training job. This approach ensures efficient and streamlined management of network slices throughout their life cycle.

Similarly, Zaidi et al. proposed an ML as a Service (MLaaS) approach for 5G IoT, employing an MLOps framework known as TMLaaS architecture². This framework facilitates the unification of ML systems for seamless implementation, deployment, and maintenance operations. By incorporating MLOps principles, the authors address the complexities associated with managing ML models in the context of 5G and IoT.

In another study, Li et al. proposed an MLOps life cycle based on Reinforcement Learning (RL) to automate and reproduce the model development process in open radio access network (O-RAN) deployment³. The authors introduced principles and practices for developing data-derived optimal decision-making strategies. By leveraging MLOps, the RL model development process becomes automated and reproducible, facilitating efficient O-RAN deployment.

Besides, Tsourdinis et al. developed a service-aware dynamic slice allocation scheme using an MLOps-based distributed ML architecture⁴, which enables dynamic and efficient resource utilization.

¹ G. Samaras, V. Theodorou, D. Laskaratos, N. Psaromanolakis, M. Mertiri, and A. Valantasis, "QMP: A Cloud-native MLOps Automation Platform for Zero-Touch Service Assurance in 5G Systems," in Proc. IEEE Int. Mediterranean Conf. on Communications and Networking (MeditCom), Sep. 2022.

² S. A. R. Zaidi, A. M. Hayajneh, M. Hafeez, and Q. Z. Ahmed, "Unlocking Edge Intelligence Through Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML)," IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 100 867–100 877, Sep. 2022.

³ P. Li et al., "RLOps: Development Life-Cycle of Reinforcement Learning Aided Open RAN," IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 113 808–113 826, Oct. 2022.

⁴ T. Tsourdinis, I. Chatzistefanidis, N. Makris, and T. Korakis, "AI-driven Service-aware Real-time Slicing for beyond 5G Networks," in Proc. IEEE INFOCOM 2022 - IEEE Conf. on Computer Communications Workshops, May. 2022.

On the other hand, the challenges of developing XAI methods and demonstrating how causal inference plays a role in 6G technology has been highlighted⁵. Similarly, in⁶, the significance of explainability in 5G is highlighted for essential services and device-to-device architectural security. Additionally, the importance of causal inference in 6G technology is emphasized.

Researchers in⁷ also acknowledge the importance of explainability in upcoming 6G networks, especially regarding its applications in resolving handover and resource allocation issues. In a comparative study⁸ of XAI techniques, SHAP is suggested as the most effective method for identifying the cause of service level agreement (SLA) violations. However, these studies focus on *post-hoc* explainability and lack the use of quantitative metrics to evaluate the fidelity of explanations and consider it during the training process in an *in-hoc* fashion, which is required to generate trustworthy models from the origin.

7.1.2 Standardization

Alongside research contributions, some organizations' initiatives are relevant for MLOps components in telecommunications. The European telecommunications standards institute experiential networked intelligence (ETSI ENI) is defining a cognitive network management architecture leveraging AI techniques. The architecture aims to provide fully automated service provision, operation, and assurance.

The corresponding closed-loop AI mechanisms can be leveraged in the MLOps lifecycle. Unlike ETSI ENI, which focuses on AI techniques, European telecommunication standards institute zero-touch service management (ETSI ZSM)⁹ is investigating automation challenges faced by operators and vertical industries. The group works on end-to-end (E2E) architecture and services automation to solve radical changes in the way networks are managed and orchestrated in the pivotal deployment of 5G and network slicing. In this intent, an MLOps approach with lifecycle management of ML models for reproducible ML pipelines would be necessary.

7.2 Gaps Analysis of MLOps for Networks

The stakeholders in network slicing ecosystem need innovations to natively embed MLOps into the network architecture while enhancing the interpretability of the black-

⁵ Y. Xiao, G. Shi, and M. Krunz, "Towards ubiquitous AI in 6G with federated learning," ArXiv, vol. abs/2004.13563, 2020.

⁶ P. Muñoz, I. de la Bandera, E. J. Khatib, A. Gómez-Andrades, I. Serrano, and R. Barco, "Root cause analysis based on temporal analysis of metrics toward self-organizing 5G networks," IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 2811–2824, 2017.

⁷ C. Li, W. Guo, S. C. Sun, S. Al-Rubaye, and A. Tsourdos, "Trustworthy deep learning in 6G-enabled mass autonomy: From concept to quality-of-trust key performance indicators," IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 112–121, 2020.

⁸ A. Terra, R. Inam, S. Baskaran, P. Batista, I. Burdick, and E. Fersman, "Explainability methods for identifying Root-cause of SLA violation prediction in 5G network," in GLOBECOM 2020 - 2020 IEEE Global Communications Conference, 2020, pp. 1–7.

⁹ ETSI ZSM 009-1, Zero-touch network and service management (zsm); closed loop automation; enablers. V0.10.5, (2021-01).

box AI decision-making process to attain human trust. In this regard, the main gaps in MLOps for networking can be summarized as follows:

- **Transparent AI:** this assumes the incorporation of explainability into the MLOps pipeline, where XAI metrics can be included as a hyperparameter or observation to trigger the re-training of AI models and control their transparency. In this respect, several metrics exist such as *confidence*, *log-odd*, and *comprehensiveness*¹⁰.
- **Cost-effective workload:** where the concept of transfer learning and model reusability are necessary to avoid re-training when it comes to similar tasks. This similarity can be characterized by a statistical distance such as the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between the weights of models after the first training. This would allow a dramatic reduction in training cost.
- **Monitoring data:** MLOps needs robust solutions for data lineage, tracking, and monitoring. Improving monitoring data for MLOps involves standardizing data formats like JSON for ease of analysis, collecting high-granularity metrics and logs, enabling real-time streaming (e.g., via Kafka or HTTP), implementing distributed tracing using tools like Jaeger or Zipkin to capture end-to-end interactions, and including contextual metadata (e.g., model version, hyperparameters) for effective issue diagnosis.
- **Hyperparameters tracking:** numerous MLOps tools are actively addressing the challenge of tracking hyperparameters, dependencies, and code versions effectively. Tools like MLflow, Kubeflow, and DVC (Data Version Control) offer solutions to monitor and manage hyperparameters alongside code and data versions, ensuring reproducibility and transparency in machine learning experiments. These platforms streamline the tracking of essential elements, aiding in model development and lifecycle management within the rapidly evolving field of machine learning operations.

¹⁰ B. Brik, H. Chergui, L. Zanzi, F. Devoti, A. Ksentini, M.S. Siddiqui, X. Costa-Perez, and C. Verikoukis, (2023). A Survey on Explainable AI for 6G O-RAN: Architecture, Use Cases, Challenges and Research Directions. ArXiv, abs/2307.00319.

Distributed MLOps Architecture for Future-Proof 6G Networks

7.3 SliceOps: Transparent MLOps Architecture for 6G

Similarly to the separation between user plane (UP) and control plane (CP), a modular and scalable integration of AI/ML as a native component into the future-proof 6G architecture would require gathering all the MLOps in a dedicated plane that can be designed in practice as a distributed cross-domain slice, which would manage the life cycle of AI models and deliver them as artifacts tailored to the target technological domain of a given network slice. This would encourage model reusability when it comes to similar tasks, reduce training workload, and thereby carbon footprint. This 6GENABLERS-AI architecture is termed SliceOps¹¹.

Figure 1 AI/ML plane.

7.3.1 SliceOps Lifecycle

The SliceOps foundation relies on a practice aiming to standardize production methods through incorporating the concept of CI and CD, producing thereby reliable software and AI solutions in short cycles. In 6G AI-native networks, SliceOps modular design allows the evolution, upgrade, and scaling of the MLOps layer and its AI functions separately from the service layers.

Figure 1 depicts the pictorial representation of an operationalizing AI-native slice deployed at the top of the network slicing environment with multiple SliceOps instances. The instances provide AI services to the corresponding slice (e.g., URLLC), and they can collaborate for specific tasks like resource allocation, where resources are generally shared between service slices. On the other hand, SliceOps guarantees AI performance isolation through triggering re-training, which means that if a SliceOps instance degrades for one slice, it will have minimum effect on the other slices. This is in line with containerized solutions that decouple the execution of iterative processes which is a necessity in ML pipelines. The SliceOps adheres to the below fundamental pipeline principles based on RL algorithms:

¹¹ F. Rezazadeh, H. Chergui, L. Alonso, and C. Verikoukis, "SliceOps: Explainable MLOps for Streamlined Automation-Native 6G Networks," in IEEE Wireless Communications (Accepted). [Online] Available: ArXiv, abs/2307.01658.

Figure 2 The SliceOps workflow including monitoring, re-training, and deploying ML model as a service.

- Monitoring System and Data Collection (1):** It is considered as a backbone step in ML practices where data acquisition is utilized for data preparation and model design processes. It allows SliceOps agents that run as containers instances within slices to collect real-time monitoring data from the gNodeB (gNB) platform of multiple key performance indicators (KPIs), encompassing available resources, number of connected devices, bandwidth utilization, channel quality, etc. This component can store structured and unstructured data on a very large scale. Such data is streamed through e.g., a Kafka bus to which the SliceOps AI functions can subscribe and fetch the relevant data under a specific Kafka topic name. The obtained data is used as input of the pipeline to guide the definition of policy in the form of service prediction. The SliceOps RL-based agent collects data on-the-fly (online RL) interacting with the slice environment or initializes the process with a pre-collected dataset (offline RL) stored in an internal database. The online RL can bring additional risks in terms of interacting with live environment and collected data. To solve this, we consider step 2, 6, and 8.
- Data Engineering and Model Loading (2, 3):** This component is responsible for data preprocessing or preparation. Different optimization targets and AI services require heterogeneous training data for neural networks. This process takes raw data from the monitoring system and transforms it into an understandable format for RL such as OpenAI Gym. The raw data contains errors and inconsistencies while having various attributes or patterns. For example, the monitored data of different slice domains can be non-Euclidean or not meeting independent and identically distributed (IID) dataset features. With the various forms of data in network slicing, pursuing the techniques such as assessment of data quality, data cleaning, data transformation, reduction of data, etc., is a vital step for better learning performance. The next step is to create neural network architecture and hyperparameters tuning before compiling and loading them into a model. The hyperparameter tuning depends highly on capability, scenario, and technology

used¹². Different datasets require setting different hyperparameters to guide the model to predict accurately in the following steps.

- **Model Training, Evaluation and Saving (4, 5, 6):** This module of SliceOps is segregated into a set of processes for the execution of continuous model training automatically with processed data. The ML model training runs a local optimization task, while the model explanation involves an *explainer*, either attribution-based (e.g., Integrated Gradient, Saliency Maps) or perturbation-based (e.g., SHAP¹³). Upon the evaluation of RL reward including interpretability metric, the model retraining is triggered whenever there is a model performance deterioration following new training data arrival (new unexplored states). Note that the reward should also correlate with slice targets (SLA, KPIs, etc.), while the interpretability refers to XAI metrics (attributions-based entropy, confidence, log-odds, fidelity, etc.) depending on the SLA adopted by the slice tenant. In this respect, a feedback loop between the explainer and the model is necessary to feed the model optimizer with the measured XAI metrics, enabling thereby explainability-aware learning. Finally, in case the model fulfills the target performance, it will be registered and stored in the model registry to be promoted into production later.
- **AI Service Provisioning (7, 8):** The next step after training and evaluation is to retrieve the registered model for encapsulation and move to the production stage in the form of a model prediction service. The trained model is continuously exposed and delivered to slices as representational state transfer (REST) application programming interface (API) assisted with SliceOps agents. The framework considers continuous monitoring in different steps to ensure model performance.

7.3.2 ETSI ZSM Compliance

The design of SliceOps solution closely adheres to the ZSM framework. The standardization process for ETSI ZSM is still in its early stages, with preliminary specifications based on a high level of abstraction. The core concept of the closed-loop AI system is to utilize context-aware and metadata-driven policies to allow for efficient and fast identification as well as incorporate new conditions while updating knowledge and making robust and actionable decisions. As shown in Figure 1, SliceOps is a practice toward deploying a more realistic closed-loop scheme to fulfill viable automation solutions for network slicing control. SliceOps manages the lifecycle of AI models in a closed-loop way that includes model performance monitoring, re-training, and delivery. It extends the ZSM framework to manage, besides the service functions, the underlying AI functions, which are natively supported in a standalone slice.

7.3.3 O-RAN Slicing Compliance

¹² F. Rezazadeh, H. Chergui, L. Alonso, and C. Verikoukis, “Continuous Multi-objective Zero-touch Network Slicing via Twin Delayed DDPG and OpenAI Gym,” in Proc. IEEE Glob. Commun. Conf., Dec. 2020.

¹³ S. M. Lundberg and S. Lee, “A Unified Approach to Interpreting Model Predictions,” in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30, 2017.

The SliceOps framework can be adapted to use case 3 of O-RAN slicing, which is related to resource allocation optimization, requirements, and architecture¹⁴. Specifically, SliceOps layer can be developed as rApps at the non-real-time (non-RT) radio intelligent controller (RIC). Thanks to its architecture that brings valuable differentiators by leveraging XAI and CI/CD, SliceOps would implement new use cases with agility and automate network operations. In this respect, rApps need to access abundant monitoring data---such as traffic load, latency, and signal strength---through the O1 interface to efficiently carry out their designated functions in time-demanding training procedures. Then, the model or policy trained by SliceOps can be packaged as an artifact and delivered via the A1 interface to run on the Near-RT RIC interface as xApp. This model deployment is performed using REST APIs over HTTP for the transfer of such JSON objects. For dynamic network optimization purposes, this xApp would control the underlying O-RAN components, namely, the central unit-control plane (O-CU-CP), different slice open central unit-user plane (O-CU-UP), and open distributed unit plane (O-DU) by using the E2 interface. The E2 interface encompasses two protocols, namely the E2 application protocol (E2AP) and the E2 service model (E2SM).

7.4 Benefits of the Architecture

The advantages of defining an AI plane in the architecture can be summarized as follows:

- **Scalability/Evolution:**
 - Efficient Resource Allocation: Separating the AI plane allows for dedicated resources for AI-related tasks, such as model inference and data processing. This improves the scalability of AI workloads, enabling the allocation of additional computing resources as needed for growing data volumes and computational demands.
 - Easier Upgrades: The AI plane's isolation makes it easier to evolve and update AI models, algorithms, and processing pipelines without disrupting other system components. This agility supports the rapid integration of new AI technologies and improvements.
- **Modularity:**
 - Clear Role Separation: Defining an AI plane provides a clear separation of responsibilities between AI-related tasks and other system functions. This modular architecture simplifies system design and maintenance, making it easier to manage and troubleshoot AI components independently.
 - Customization and Interchangeability: Modularity in the AI plane allows for the customization and interchangeability of AI models and algorithms. Teams can experiment with different AI approaches and integrate them seamlessly into the system.
- **Reusability:**
 - Reusable AI Components: A well-defined AI plane encourages the development of reusable AI components, such as pre-trained models, data preprocessing modules, and feature extraction pipelines. These

¹⁴ O-RAN.WG1, "Slicing Architecture Technical Specification 9.0," in ORAN Specifications, March 2023.

components can be shared across multiple projects and applications, promoting efficiency and consistency.

- Interoperability: Reusable AI components within the AI plane can be integrated into various applications and services, enhancing interoperability and reducing the need to reinvent AI solutions for each use case.

8 Tools to Implement the Architecture

This section provides background information regarding available tools to support MLOps which will be investigated in this project as potential solutions for implementing the proposed architecture. Please, note that this section does not aim to cover all available tools but rather to present an overview of the different tools available, with a focus on those that are open source. To this end, we have structured this section into two main subsections. Specifically, Subsection 9.1 presents a subset of MLOps tools by considering their main role in the MLOps lifecycle while Subsection 9.2 introduces some popular platforms capable of performing E2E MLOps.

9.1 MLOps Tools

MLOps tools reduce the time and complexity of managing, deploying, and monitoring ML models. Moreover, they enhance communication and collaboration across teams (e.g., operations, data science, and development teams), thus reducing conflicts, accelerating the release of new features, and improving the quality of the models.

MLOps tools have been grouped into four categories based on their main functionality within the MLOps lifecycle. A typical MLOps workflow is mainly composed of the following phases: data processing (e.g., data extraction and data transformation), model training (e.g., model training and validation), model deployment, and model monitoring.

Data processing tools can be categorized into two main groups: data labeling or preprocessing tools and data versioning tools. Data versioning tools manage different versions of data and store them in an accessible and well-organized manner. Examples of these tools are DVC, LakeFS, and Delta Lake.

Model training tools encompass a wide range of functionalities, including feature engineering, experiment tracking, and hyperparameter optimization. Feature engineering tools, such as AutoFet, significantly expedite the feature extraction process. Experiment tracking tools like MLflow enable the storage of information about the different experiments. Furthermore, hyperparameter tuning tools like Talos automate the process of identifying those hyperparameters that optimize the performance of machine learning models.

Model deployment or model serving tools, exemplified by Seldon Core, facilitate the seamless integration of ML models in the target environment, allowing for predictions to be served to end-users or downstream systems. Seldon Core is a cloud-agnostic framework for deploying ML models and experiments at scale on Kubernetes.

Model monitoring tools, such as Evidently AI and MLRun, play a crucial role in detecting model degradation and anomalies over time. They also enable the setup of alerts in the event of performance issues. Evidently AI, in particular, allows for the monitoring of ML models throughout the development, validation, and production stages.

9.2 E2E MLOps Platforms

Regarding End-to-end MLOps platforms, there is a diverse array of open-source platforms available, including Kubeflow, MLflow, and Polyaxon. These platforms offer tools for managing all stages of the ML lifecycle in a more straightforward, reliable, and efficient manner.

*Kubeflow*¹⁵ can be used for data preprocessing, model training, model optimization, prediction serving, and monitoring in production environments. It simplifies the deployment of ML models on Kubernetes. The workloads can be deployed locally, on-premise, or in cloud environments¹⁶. Figure 3 provides an overview of the Kubeflow platform components.

Figure 3 Kubeflow model architecture¹⁶

*MLflow*¹⁷ platform consists of four components (i.e., tracking, projects, models, and model registry) that enable the management of the ML lifecycle. Specifically, it provides support for experimentation, reproducibility, deployment, and a central repository for storing and managing ML models. It can handle and execute any ML library and any programming language¹⁸. However, it has certain limitations such as a lack of full customizability and the absence of built-in notebooks.

*Polyaxon*¹⁹ is primarily oriented toward experiment tracking and visualization, parallel executions, and hyperparameter optimization. It relies on Kubernetes to create

¹⁵ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

¹⁶ G. Recupito et al., "A Multivocal Literature Review of MLOps Tools and Features," 2022 48th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), Gran Canaria, Spain, 2022, pp. 84-91, doi: 10.1109/SEAA56994.2022.00021.

¹⁷ <https://mlflow.org>

¹⁸ N. Hewage and D. Meedeniya, "Machine learning operations: A survey on MLOps tool support," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2202.10169*, 2022.

¹⁹ <https://polyaxon.com/>

repeatable and executable deployments, thus is not fully architecture agnostic. It can be deployed on-premise or in the cloud.

*TensorFlow Extended (TFX)*²⁰ is a robust, flexible, and scalable framework designed for training, deploying, and maintaining ML models. It also offers features for model versioning and management.

Table 1 summarizes the main tasks in the MLOps lifecycle supported by these frameworks. From this table, we can appreciate that despite the availability of several MLOps platforms, many of them have limitations regarding mainly tasks related to data processing (DP) and operation and monitoring (OM) phases. Additionally, not all these tools can be seamlessly integrated, potentially leading to compatibility issues. Therefore, there is still work to be done in developing user-friendly and fully automated MLOps platforms.

Table 1 MLOps platforms supported capabilities in the MLOps phases²¹.

Phase	Data Preprocessing (DP)						Model Training (MT)					Model Deployment (MD)			Operations and Monitoring (OM)		
Platform	DP-1	DP-2	DP-3	DP-4	DP-5	DP-6	MT-1	MT-2	MT-3	MT-4	MT-5	MD-1	MD-2	MD-3	OM-1	OM-2	OM-3
Kubeflow (v1.3.0)		x			x		x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		
MLFlow (v1.14.1)									x	x		x	x	x			
Polyaxon (v1.9.5)					x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
TFX (v0.30.0)		x	x	x	x							x	x	x		x	x

DP-1: Data Source Handling

DP-2: Data Preprocessing and Transformations

DP-3: Data Quality Measurement Support through Metrics

DP-4: Data Management

DP-5: Data Versioning

DP-6: Data Labeling

MT-1: Model Type Selection

MT-2: Hyperparameter Tuning

MT-3: Tracking

MT-4: Integration Friendly

MT-5: Code Versioning

MD-1: Model Packaging

MD-2: Model Registry

MD-3: Support for Different Deployment Patterns

OM-1: System Monitoring

OM-2: Input Data Monitoring

OM-3: Model's Performance Monitoring

²⁰ <https://www.tensorflow.org/?hl=es-419>

²¹ P. Ruf et al., "Demystifying MLOps and presenting a recipe for the selection of open-source tools," in Applied Sciences 11.19: 8861, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11198861>.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined a comprehensive 6GENABLERS-IA AI/ML Operations (MLOps) architecture, spanning from edge devices to cloud infrastructure. It encompasses training, inference operations, and Lifecycle management (LCM) for AI processes. The report extensively examines MLOps in the context of network automation, addressing both research and standardization aspects. A gap analysis reveals the need to seamlessly integrate MLOps into future-proof 6G networks while improving the transparency of AI decision-making for human trust. The proposed architecture, known as SliceOps, involves consolidating AI model LCM within a dedicated AI plane, forming a standalone cross-domain slice. The document also explores compliance with ETSI ZSM and O-RAN standards and underscores the advantages of this architecture. Furthermore, it discusses the tools and platforms that can be employed to implement the proposed framework, offering a holistic view of its practical application in the network slicing ecosystem.